

Determination of Iodide by Chloramine-T at Room Temperature

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Iodide has been determined at room temperature, through oxidation to iodate with chloramine-T and titrating the iodate formed iodometrically.

RECENTLY Venkappaya and Aravamudan¹ have reported a method for the determination of iodide. They used excess of chloramine-T (CAT) to oxidise iodide to iodate :

The iodate formed in the reaction was determined iodometrically after destroying excess of CAT with dimethylsulphoxide. Their method, although accurate, is cumbersome for the reaction mixture has to be kept at 50°-60° for 10 min before determination can be completed. The present paper describes the conditions in which iodide can be determined at room temperature.

Commercially available CAT was thrice recrystallised before use. All other chemicals were of analytical grade (BDH Analar or Merck GR). Iodide solution was prepared by dissolving potassium iodide in distilled water and standardised by Volhard's method.

Procedure

To a suitable aliquot, containing 15-40 mg of iodide ion in a titration flask, was added 2 g of potassium biphthalate and an excess of 0.1M CAT solution (5-10 ml). After 2-3 min, 10 ml of 5% potassium bromide solution followed by 10 ml of 2% sodium formate solution were added and the reaction mixture

was kept for another 5 min 2 g of potassium iodide were then added and after 2-3 min the iodine liberated was titrated with 0.1N sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. The results are given in the Table.

In biphthalate buffer of pH 4 the oxidation of iodide to iodate, with excess of CAT, is completed within 2-3 min at room temperature. The completion of the reaction is seen by disappearance of yellow colour due to intermediate iodine formation. The excess of CAT is destroyed by liberating bromine from excess potassium bromide :

and the bromine in its turn is destroyed with sodium formate :

The iodate is then determined by adding potassium iodide and titrating the iodine liberated with sodium thiosulphate.

The method is applicable in the presence of bromide. It has been observed that in biphthalate buffer excess of CAT liberates bromine from bromide. However, bromine gets reduced with formate prior to iodate determination and therefore bromide does not interfere.

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Reference

1. D. VENKAPPAYA and G. ARAVAMUDAN, *Talanta*, 1974, 21, 358.

TABLE—ESTIMATION OF IODIDE

Amount taken (mg)	0.1N Iodine liberated (ml)	Amount found (mg)
17.41	8.25	17.45
20.31	9.60	20.30
23.21	10.95	23.16
26.11	12.35	26.02
29.01	13.65	28.86
31.91	15.10	31.93